

CITY OF SABADELL

Sabadell is a Spanish City of 208.256 inhabitants (2013) located in the Barcelona Metropolitan Region and benefiting from a strategic position in southern Europe, close to a world city like Barcelona, well connected to main infrastructures linking the Mediterranean coast to the rest of Europe. Sabadell has also succeeded in preserving its personality despite being only 25 km from Barcelona. This is due to the strong historical will of its population of being active in promoting initiatives in all fields: economic, cultural and social. This is why Sabadell is headquartering two corporations present at the IBEX 35 (Stock exchange index, with the 35 Spanish biggest firms), hosts an Opera Theater (La Faràndula) and has inaugurated one of the best indoor athletic courts in Spain.

Sabadell has also a remarkable contemporary history, when at the beginning of the XX century was called the “Catalan Manchester” due to the big presence of textile industries. Due to pressure from cheaper markets, textile industries have declined in number but increased in quality, boosted by the Sabadell School of Design. Moreover, Sabadell is located in an area surrounding the B-30 orbital highway (known as B30 axis) hosting near 23,000 firms, a big university (UAB), an international business school (ESADE) and a modern industrial-scale synchrotron (Alba). Therefore, the city is well-prepared for the new economy.

Last, but not least, Sabadell is well-known for having found a good balance between life quality and economic prosperity. This is due to the political orientation of the city as of the early 80s, where citizens have been given the main role. For this reason, the construction of the impressive financial axis of Sabadell (Eix Macià) in mid 90s came together with the development of the big Catalunya Park just in front of it, and the recuperation of previously polluted areas surrounding the Ripoll river for leisure uses, as well as ecological agricultural production.

www.sabadell.cat

SABADELL SMART CITY (<http://www.sabadell.cat/ca/smartcity>)

As experts are predicting, the XXI century will be the century of cities, just as the XX century was that of nation-states and the XIX century that of empires. Cities like Sabadell are becoming key axes for economic growth, innovation, social progress, culture, knowledge and diversity. This strategic focus on cities goes in parallel with the boom of ICTs based on the Internet -the so-called “digital revolution” or the generalization in the use of smart phones-, the need to reduce energy consumption both for environmental and economic reasons and the need to allocate resources in a most efficient way, mainly economic, due to economic context. **“Sabadell ciutat intel·ligent, smart city”** strategy is born within this context and intends to harmonically match the 3 aforementioned elements: transforming urban management and being environmentally and economically exemplary by taking advantage of innovative technological developments.

The project started on 2009 through the implementation of innovative ICTs at particular areas of urban management, especially in the field of energy efficiency and sustainability, at that time still in a quite scattered, not fully-connected approach. Relevant examples of those early initiatives are the remote management of irrigation in Sabadell’s parks and gardens, and the distribution to citizens of free “smart” domestic meters in order to raise their awareness about the impact of daily activities on the environment and their energy bills.

As of 2012, a master plan has been established in order to connect all previous initiatives (2009-2011), while at the same time new actions are being implemented or envisaged, under the umbrella of the brand **“Sabadell ciutat intel·ligent, smart city”**. The transformation process behind this project is a long-term one, embracing all areas of local government, benefiting from intensive use of ICTs and cooperating with other public institutions and private corporations, promoting Public Private Partnerships.

DESIGN & IMPLEMENTATION

The Sabadell City Council is completely committed to the **“Sabadell ciutat intel·ligent, smart city”** strategy and is working intensively for its implementation. The City Council has designed a work methodology involving all main actors of the sector (internal and external) to jointly develop the plan initiatives.

The main objective of the work methodology is the definition of a **PROJECTS CATALOG** with the collaboration of internal and external important actors. This is a crosswise document development, involving all the City Council areas. Currently 34 projects have been designed.

The external main actors involved in the projects catalog definition have been grouped in a **PARTNERSHIP**, consisting of 27 institutions which meets quarterly. Also, this partnership gives technical assessment to the projects developed within the strategy. The current members are:

Apart from the work methodology, the City Council is participating in different key international and national networks in order to promote the strategy and make the most of the synergies existing between cities and Institutions. Relevant examples of this networks are:

- **COVENANT OF MAYORS**
- **SPANISH NETWORK FOR SMART CITIES (RECI)**
- **AENOR STANDARDIZATION COMMITTEE FOR SMART CITIES**
- **CITY PROTOCOL SOCIETY**
- **EUROPEAN CIVITAS FORUM and CIVINET Spain & Portugal**

Also, recognition are basic requirements for the strategy to succeed. We can highlight the following funds and prizes already achieved:

- World Smart City Awards 2013, finalists at the City Category.
- Civitas Award 2013, finalists at the Technical Innovation Category.
- Access City Award 2013, semifinalists.
- WeGo Prize 2012, winner to best e-government.
- SEMS-2011 Prize (*Spanish Sustainable Mobility Week*), finalist
- ManagEnergy Local Energy Action Award 2011, category “Awareness and information projects” (Nominees)
- Green Building 2010 National Prize, “Most innovative project”

OBJECTIVES

1. **Real time information:** Increase the real-time information available to the citizens to increase their level of awareness of their city whilst promoting the City Council's transparency.
2. **Reduce public expenditure in municipal services:** Implement remote management systems, consumption monitoring and use of technological devices for a better control and cost decrease.
3. **Improve efficiency and quality of public services:** Implement technologies to improve service quality and efficiency, enabling a proactive management and simplifying and automating administrative processes.
4. **Sabadell as a model for smart management:** Sabadell as a leading city in implementing a smart city model, hosting companies that wish to test their new technologies in the city, and citizens interested in “technological tourism”.
5. **Boosting the knowledge economy:** The present crisis imposes a reform in productive sectors in order to generate new ideas and meeting points for entrepreneurs, researchers and investors, as well as promoting new concepts like co-working, networking, e-learning or e-commerce.
6. **Sustainability:** The smart city model implies innovative management measures in reducing demand of fossil fuel and decreasing CO2 emissions, etc. in order to fulfill the goals for 2020 established by the EU Smart Cities Initiative.

SABADELL SMART CONGRESS

Also the City of Sabadell hosts annually a Smart Congress, which takes place during the first semester of the year.

<http://www.sabadellsmartcongress.com/>

EXPERTISE IN ENERGY EFFICIENCY

The City of Sabadell has worked intensively in different projects related to energy efficiency. We can highlight:

1. Public lighting:

- a. currently, a contract with an service company (ESCO) has been implemented for public lighting management and investments, with the following targets:
 - Average yearly savings of more than 1 milion euro during the contract period (2012 – 2022), provided that energy prices increase at an 8% rate per year.
 - 29% of lamps equipped with LED technology.
 - 79% of light points equipped with flow regulator.
 - 30% of energy savings and 847 Tn decrease in CO2 emissions per year, once the investment is executed.
- b. 27 measures implying more energy efficiency and energy savings, including:
 - Installation of 107 electronic ballasts with flow regulation.
 - Installation of remote point to point control via radio at 32 lights.
 - Renewal of lighting in seven city areas (312 luminaries, supports, lines, electrical panels, etc. ...) and lighting panels in “Gran Via” street (total 15 units).
 - Incorporating billing management software in order to adjust the contracted power, increase control in case of irregularities and improve the monitoring of energy expenditure.

S/t objective: Remote management of public lighting at “Passeig de la Plaça Major” boulevard:

- 1st. phase (11 columns and 25 lights)
 1. “Plaça de l’Àngel” square: 1 multi spotlight column with 5 lights.
 2. “Passeig de Manresa” boulevard: 5 columns with 1 light each, 2 columns with 2 lights each, 3 columns with three lights each.
 3. “Carrer de la Palanca” street: Replacement of lights embedded in the facade, by wall arm with 1 luminary.

2. Public facilities - smart buildings:

- a. Adopted measures for energy saving at municipal facilities:
 - Remote management of heating at 59 buildings
 - 39 municipal facilities with solar thermal energy installations (1,972.89 sqm)
 - 9 municipal facilities with photovoltaic energy (with 138,9 kWp power)
 - 5 municipal facilities equipped with geothermal energy (with 2,087.2 kW power)
 - Installation of 45 capacitor batteries that allow reactive power compensation.
 - Network analyzers at 41 municipal facilities to continuously monitor consumption and electric parameters.
 - Monitoring at 2 hot domestic water (HDW) production facilities through solar thermal collectors (Cal Balsach and Sant Oleguer).
 - Air conditioning centralized control in 7 facilities and control of lighting in 4 facilities.
 - Lighting remote management with motion and ambient light sensors at “Escola Illa” (implemented at 401 lights) and at “Escola Romànica”.
 - Pilot test of new lighting efficient systems (LED lighting) in “Can Marcet” administrative building.
 - Remote management of solar installations with the “Solarweb” system:
 - Automating the management of solar installations in public buildings.
 - Establishing protocols for energy management.
 - Detecting errors remotely.
 - Reduced maintenance costs.
 - Data collection of energy production from these facilities.

S/t objective: complete maintenance of 12 municipal facilities through an ESCO model.

3. Traffic lights: 100% of traffic light optical equipped with LED technology. This has implied:
 - 1,165,616 kwh energy consumption decrease
 - 210,976 kg CO2 emission decrease
 - 138,000 euro savings
4. Smart meters: during 2009 – 2013 a campaign with Smart Meters has been made (real-time electricity consumption metering), where smart meters have been distributed into some Sabadell homes for a 6 month period. This initiative was selected by the Covenant of Mayors as a successful example in the battle against climate change and was selected as Nominees at ManagEnergy Local Energy Action Award 2011, category “Awareness and information projects”. It has been structured into 5 phases (100 dwellings involved):
 - Phase 1, pilot test (2009-2010): 28 dwellings in Creu Alta and Creu de Barberà.
 - Phase 2, West sector (2010-2011): 22 dwellings.
 - Phase 3, North sector (2011-2012): 22 dwellings.
 - Phase 4, East-Centre sector: 15 dwellings in Covadonga, Nostra Llar, Torre-romeu, Centre-Est, Can Roqueta, Raval d’Amàlia, el Poblenou and Sol i Padrís neighbourhoods.
 - Phase 5, 2013-2014: 22 families who have installed the counter in December.

It has achieved an estimated reduction of 3,022 kg/year in greenhouse gases emissions (12.5% decrease in energy consumption).

M/t objective:

- European Project “District of the Future”:
 - It is a FP7 project for the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation within the Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development. Also known as A Modular Open Big Data Energy Optimising Framework for cities.
 - It will be developed by a Consortium of 11 partners from Spain, UK, France and Finland, led by Telefonica. Three Cities are participating as demonstrators: Sabadell, Orleans (FR) and Corby (UK).
 - It started on November 2013 and will be developed for 3 years.
 - Sabadell is participating with the installation of smart meters in “Can Marçet” administrative building, “Can Llong” Pneumatic waste collection central building and “Can Llong 4” residential building.

- Energy management in Sabadell dwellings:
 - Domestic energy saving campaign.
 - Software to help manage household energy.
 - Intended to 300 homes, with exclusive cession of specialized software during 3 years

H2020 ENERGY: FUTURE PROJECTS AND INTEREST

As said the City of Sabadell is developing a Projects Catalogue document within the Smart City Strategy, which can give an indication along with all the above mentioned, of the H2020 interests of the City in Energy Calls.

1. LED technology in street lighting (2nd phase)
2. Energy service company contract (ESCO) for 15 municipal facilities (lighting only)
3. ESCO for 15 municipal facilities with renewable energies
4. ESCO for 12 municipal facilities
5. Energy consumption monitoring (electricity, gas and water)
6. Smart grids development